

The Administrative System of District Muzaffargarh 1901-1970

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Received on: 09-10-2022

Accepted on: 17-11-2022

Abstract

After the start of the great game colonial government felt the need of extension to cross the Indus and entered in Punjab. In the successes of the 2nd Sikh war in 1849 British forces occupied Punjab. They announced the annexation and divided the Punjab in different new administrative units. The established new administrative zones as divisions and districts. Layyah was made as a Divisional Head Quarter, While Khangarh was declared as a district of Layyah division. In 1861 Layyah lost its divisional and district status and Muzaffargarh was declared as a district in place of Khangarh. In 1909 Tehsil Layyah became a part of district Muzaffargarh. In 1947, administratively Muzaffargarh became a part of Bahawalpur State but at the end of One Unit Muzaffargarh district added in Multan division. On 1st July 1982 Dera Ghazi Khan was announced as a new division, Layyah tehsil was upgrade as district and both the districts Muzaffargarh and Layyah became the part of Dera Ghazi Khan Division.

Keywords: Muzaffargarh, Administrative, System, Backward, Region, District etc

Discussion

Muzaffargarh is situated between the two rivers Indus and Chenab. It has populated from many centuries. The district has fertile land and the natural sources are available here, Cotton, Mangoes and Dates of the district are famous in all over the Pakistan. Unfortunately the history is silent about the district, because it was very far from the center. The district Muzaffargarh was very much backward area of the sub-continent during the period of the British government in the sub-continent. It was declared, as a district in 1849. The head Quarter of the district was transferred to Muzaffargarh in 1861. People were very poor, simple and lived peacefully. They had no interest in the political situation. Therefore, in the mutiny period of 1857 had no effect in the district activities. Generally, it is said that Muzaffargarh is a peace full district. No political activity was seen in the district. Government had totally controlled over the people and all the power and the deputy commissioner as a head of the district.¹

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As in the mutiny report it is said that the people of the district have never been interest to take or organized any political activities in the district and created a disturbance in the district. They consider more favorable to the government. The people are very good in characters particularly in the tahsil of Seetpur. The people never tried to make any opposition or assist the opposition to the government.² There were few persons who have got its member ship. Nawabzada Saif Ullah khan was the only member of the Muslim League in the district and he paid the annual fund of the party and showed himself of Muslim League, s member in 1911. Therefore the deficiency of political consensus was very much in the people.³ In 1920 there was no Muslim League in the district Muzaffargarh. Sardar Abdul Hameed Khan joined Congress when there was no Muslim League. He selected the vice president of All Indian National Congress. At this time Babu Nonihal Karishan Advocate was the President of Congress in district.⁴ Although before the election I tried to convince some important personalities of the district, like Malik Qadir Bukhsh Jakhaar, Mian Fazal Karim and Ibrahim Burq. But they refused to join Muslim League. Nawabzada Nasar Ullah Khan Joined Majlis-e-Ahrar. They neglected Muslim League and later on people neglected them in the election. All they had lost their seats.⁵ Sardar Abdul Hameed Khan Dasti was a famous lawyer and he was public prosecutor. He resigned his government service and joined all India Muslim League. Sardar Abdul Hameed Khan was the chief of a big Bloch tribe of the district. He was appointed the district president of All India Muslim League. He worked very hard during the election for the Success of Muslim League.⁶

Before the British rule the district mostly remained under the Multan province. Many dynasties ruled at the district. Langah, Nahars, Baloch and Sadozai families. After them Sikhs was in power and they occupied the district in 1818. After the Sikh the British occupied the Punjab in 1849. Now Muzaffargarh was under the rule of British administration. The district has seen lot of changes in his history.

In 1849 British government forming the district of Khangarh. At this time Muzaffargarh was the part of the Khangarh district & Tehsil. It was the head quarter of the district. But later on in 1850 it was transferred to Muzaffargarh. The district Khangarh contained the Tehsils of Khangarh and Alipur. In 1859 Khangarh district renamed as Muzaffargarh, In 1859 Kotaddu tehsil was separated from Layyah and it was added to district Muzaffargarh. Soon some other areas were also added in the district.⁷

In 1849 Layyah had become a district and in 1850 it was declared as a division. Dera Ismail Khan, Dera Ghazi Khan, Layyah and Khangarh districts were included in this division. Col. Ras was appointed its first deputy commissioner. He died in 1857 and his grave is found in the Gora Court Yard of Layyah. Later on Major Polak Deputy Commissioner of Dera Ghazi Khan and Major Brown remained the commissioner of Layyah.⁸ In 1861 Layyah was abolished and Layyah was added to district Dera Ismail Khan as a Tehsil. In 1901 Layyah was separated from Dera Ismail Khan and it was added to Mian district Mianwali. After this another change was made in 1909 when tehsil Layyah was added to district Muzaffargarh.⁹ From the administrative point of view, the district was divided into the two sub-divisions and four Tehsils, Muzaffargarh, Alipur, Kotaddu and Layyah. Deputy Commissioner was appointed for the administration. He was the most powerful officer of the district.¹⁰ The deputy commissioner is working as a head of the revenue Incharge and he is called the collector. The two other sub-divisional officers support him. They are present in sub-

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divisions at Alipur and Layyah.¹¹ In the ancient time the Hindustan was divided in many small states. However during the Mughal reign the state established properly and a central government was established. The new administrative division was created. Sher Shah Suri took some step to promote the administrative system. Later on in the reign of Akbar land reforms were brought out through new settlement. The post of Patwari was created in the Akbar, s reign.

A number of historians attribute the evolution of the revenue structure in India to Sher Shah Suri. But his reign was very short and the real work was done by the Akbar the great Mughal.¹² After 1757 Clive appointed administrators for revenue purpose. Later on Warr Hasting brought reformed about these administrators. Now they were called collector. In 1774 the post of collector was abolished. But in 1776 it was restored. After the administrative reforms in 1784 the post of district judge was created and he was given the authorities of Magistrate. District collector was only the responsible for revenue.¹³ All the courts work and magistracy work was given to the judges. In 1818 Police and the Magistrates were under the control of the judges. The duty of the district Magistrate was to maintain the law and order situation and collect revenue. In 1829 Wilam Panthic created the post of commissioner. In 1831 the session work was given to the district judge than commissioner, while the magistracy work was given to the collector. After 1857 the deputy commissioner had become powerful, he was given the authorities of district Magistrate. In 1919 some authorities were transferred to the Municipal institutes.¹⁴

The concentration of all the responsibilities on one officer cannot fail to keep his attention alive and to stimulate his energy in every department to the utmost whilst it will preclude the growth of those instructions to good government which are apt to spring up where two co-ordinate the officers divide the authority. Now his authorities were as;

District officer as a collector

District officer as a district Magistrate

District officer as a public relation officer

District officer as a representative of government.¹⁵

We know politics nominally and it means the maintenance of the stability of the state and its existing system. When the political stakes are high, particularly in developing nations, the nature and seriousness of threats to the stability if the state becomes an important factor seeking solution. The need for stability obviously creates a field organization quite different from the one, which one would expect from a developed and stable society. Again the effect field organization playing key role in stabling process as the side factor of pressure for fragmentation of power between disparate. Agencies/departments/branches of the bureaucracy. Thus the nature & seriousness of threats to stability must determine the character of field administration.¹⁶

In this prospect it is said that the deputy commissioner was the ruler of the district. He had a full command in the district. The British government controlled the country through him. British government divided in many small units for administration. This small administrative unit is called district. Deputy Commissioner is the head of it. And the district was under the general charge of the Deputy Commissioner, who was a district Magistrate as well as the District Collector.¹⁷ After the emergence of Pakistan in 1947 the deputy commissioner was the strong and powerful office and the head of the district. He had more

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than hundred kinds of authorities. From 1947 to 1978 about 44 documents were prepared to bring reforms about the authorities of the deputy commissioner. In 1971 Assistant commissioner were appointed and they had the authorities of revenue. In 1979 the local government system was established and it decreased the powers of deputy commissioner. The first Muslim Deputy Commissioner of the district was Molvi Inam Ullah. After Pakistan the deputy commissioner was Raja Lal Hussain. It was famous as a Kikar Singh and he was the loyalist and supporter of unionists during the election 1945-46.

Deputy Commissioner, District Magistrate, Additional district Magistrate, Tehsildar, Naib Tehsildar are playing very important role in the district. The district was divided into Tehsils for administration. In tahsil Muzaffargarh with Tehsildar three Naib-tahsildars, nine Qanungos and 115 Patwaries were working for the revenue propose. There were 423 villages in tahsil Muzaffargarh. In tahsil Alipur there was a Tehsildar with one Naib Tehsildar at the head quarter, 8 Qanungo and ninety Patwaries. There were 207 villages in tahsil Alipur. In Tahsil Kotadu the Tehsildar was working with one Naib Tehsildar, five Qanungo and 65 Patwaries. There were 155 villages in tahsil Kotadu. In tahsil Layyah with the Tehsildar one-Naib Tehsildar, five Qanungo and ninety Patwaries were working. There were 170 villages in Tahsil Layyah.¹⁸

Income and Expenditure MC/T Committees

Sr. #.	Municipal/ Town Committee 1922-29	1961-62			
		Income (Rs)	Expenditure (Rs)	Income (Rs)	Expenditure (Rs)
1	Muzaffargarh M.C	29133	29133	254268	235298
2	Layyah M.C	41809	41809	387875	299805
3	Khangarh T.C	18652	18652	72465	57567
4	Alipur T.C	19167	19167	95056	81576
5	Jatoi T.C	--	---	29014	26535
6	Kotadu T.C	8113	5689	167522	227343
7	D.Din Panah T.C	1629	1206	11299	6907
8	Karor T.C	14810	14810	155547	138774

Name of council	1901	1922	1961	1972	1981
Distt. Council	01	01	01	1	01
Tehsils Councils	03	04	04	04	04
Union Councils	—		87		91
Town Committees	—		6	07	07
Municipal Committees 1.Muzaffargarh 2-Layyah	—		02	02	02
Tehsildar	03	04	04	04	04
Naib-Tehsildar	04	09	10	12	13
Qanungo Halqas	14	27	50	48	52
Patwaries Halqas	242	348	322	329	337

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In 1928 the board income was 535105 and expenditure was 519784 rupees. The sources of income were government aid, local rate, education, and health and district works fee. In 1960 district council was created for five years and basic democracy system was enforced.

1	Municipal Act 1867
2	Punjab District Board Act 1883
3	Municipal Act 1911
4	Small Town Act 1922
5	Town Improvement Act 1922
6	Punjab Village Act 1931
7	District Board Act 1934
8	Basic Democracy Law 1958
9	Municipal Administration Act 1960
10	Punjab people's Local ordinance 1972

In 1961-62 the income of district council was 3301007 and expenditure was 3285539 rupees.¹⁹ In 1958 Ayub khan imposed martial law, he arrogated the constitution Ayub khan had long term political motives and ambitions. All political parties were abolished and political activities were banded. Ayub khan introduced new system of local Government and he named it basic democracies. It was a different system then the local boards. Such kind of system is union council's district councils it was also an electoral college for presidential election. It was consisted on 80000 members. The election of basic democracies were held in 1960. One of the principal aim was the basic democracies was the association of the people with the administration at each level. ²⁰

Sr. No.	Institute	Elected Members	Non-Official	Official	Total
1	District Council	10	10	20	40
2	4 Tahsil Councils	93	35	40	163
3	2 Municipal Committees	07	04	03	14
4	6 Town Committees	45	22	--	67
5	7 Union Committees	31	---	--	31
6	87 Union Councils	955	416	--	1371

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11	Punjab Local Govt. Act 1975
12	Punjab Local Govt. Ordinance 1979

Sr.#	Municipal/ Town Committee	Members	Elected	Nominated	Date of Constitution
1	M. Garh M.C	9	6	3	4-6-1960
2	Layyah M.C	7	4	3	Do
3	Khangarh T.C	9	3	6	12-3-1960
4	Alipur T.C	13	9	4	26-2-1960
5	Jatoi T.C	9	6	3	1960
6	Kotadu T.C	9	14	5	26-2-1960
7	D. Din Panah T. C	6	4	2	10-11-1960
8	Karor T.C	9	6	3	do

But in district Muzaffargarh condition was different and here Ayub khan lost election due to the presence of Sardar Abdul Hameed Khan Dasti who was a great leader of freedom movement and the sincere supporter of Mother-e- Milat Fatima Jinnah.²¹

List of Zails

Sr.No.	Zail	Sr.No.	Zail	Sr.No.	Zail
1	Amirpur	19	Damarwala Shumali	37	Pirhaar Gharbi
2	Rangpur	20	Shaher Sultan	38	Shekh Umer
3	Muradabad	21	Belewala	39	Sanawan
4	Thatha Siyalan	22	Bet warhianwala	40	Khar Gharbi
5	Muzaffargarh	23	Jatoi	41	Thatha Gurmani
6	Thatha Qureshi	24	Jhalarian	42	Khoawar
7	Khangarh	25	Madwala	43	Gujrat
8	Mondka	26	Damarwala Jnobi	44	Maharanwali
9	Ali Daba	27	Bande Shah	45	Wara Sihran
10	Qalandar Wala	28	Alipur	46	Karor
11	Shrif Chajra	29	Khairpur sadat	47	Naushera
12	Kinjhar	30	Ghiri	48	Layyah
13	Diwala	31	Sitpur	49	Sarishta
14	Uttera Sandila	32	Bhambri	50	Kot Sultan
15	Mahra	33	Khanpur Naraks	51	Bet Dabli
16	Rohilanwali	34	DHAKA	52	Nawankot
17	Mochiwali	35	Tibba	-----	-----
18	Ghazanfargarh	36	Pattal Kotadu	-----	-----

Judicial point of view and the judicial system was under the district session & judge of Multan who was also the district & session judge for district Muzaffargarh. Multan was a Commissioner and the session Judge trial the cases in the head quarter. There were no murder cases in those days. There fore session judge had come to Muzaffargarh for ten

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days. But he hears the appeals in Multan.²²

At the emergence of Pakistan there was only administrative Civil Judge, Posted in Muzaffargarh. In 1954 one sub judge was posted. With the passage of time and increase in the workload .The number of members of judiciary has increased .The judicial system was consisting of the District and session judge and his co-judges of additional session and district judges. A senior civil judge and his co-civil judges of the first class, second and third class they provide justice to the people to their authorities. They have also as a charge of special magistrate a city magistrate and also a traffic magistrate in the district; they hear the criminal cases and revenue cases and the justice system is making the lives

of the people peaceful. With out judiciary the justice is not possible.²³

The number of police station has been remained unchanged in the district despite major changes in the district from its creation. To control the district and crimes 14 police stations were established later on these are extended into 18 and also established police check posts.²⁴ There fore the whole district was divided into many police stations. According to the police record brought a police act 1861 in 1861 for the peace. The Present administrative set up of Police is superintendent of police as executive head of the district who is directly responsible for all matters relating to its internal economy, training and management and also for the maintenance of discipline and efficient Performance of all its duties in the administration.²⁵

Sr. No.	Police Station	Tahsil
1	Muzaffargarh Sadar	Muzaffargarh
2	Khangarh	do
3	Rangpur	do
4	Qureshi	do
5	Kinjhar	do
6	Rohilanwali	do
7	Alipur	Alipur
8	Seetpur	do
9	Kundai	do
10	Jatoi	do
11	Shaher Sultan	do
12	Kotadu	Kotadu
13	Mahmod Kot	do
14	Daira Din Panah	do
15	Layyah	Layyah
16	Chaubara	do
17	Karor	do
18	Kot Sultan	do

Muzaffargarh remained a peaceful district as a whole in sub-continent according to the mutiny reports. The police record and the government gazetteer also shows that the district was very peaceful region.

Year	Registered Cases	Decided Cases	Punishable	Released Persons
		[7]		

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1901	1104	657	515	142
1902	1160	695	547	112
1903	1151	657	554	103
1904	1148	710	569	141
1905	1340	677	522	155
1927	1169	--	--	--
1928	1145	--	--	--

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The regular police force consists of 397 of all ranks in the under control of a Superintendent. There are four inspectors under him. The village watchmen were 489 in 1903. The number of police stations were 14. There were also one outpost and four road post. In 1928 there were 18 police stations, in these police station two inspector, 27 sub-inspector, 7 assistant sub-inspector, 86 head constables, 452 constables and 667 watchmen. These watchmen were supported police about the information of the cases and supported for investigation in the cases. After the emergence of Pakistan the Police force was increased and its strength was 707 in 1964 and 550 were constables out of 707.27

Year	Police Station	Inspector	Sub-Inspectors	ASI	H/ Constables	Constables
1929	18	02	27	07	86	452
1961	18	04	33	36	77	550
1972	18	05	42	52	107	653
1981	18	08	53	69	119	772
2007	20	14	67	92	238	1762
Institution		Strength		Beds		
Hospitals		07		310		
Dispensaries		50		57		
Rural health centers		06		48		
T.B Clinics		02		---		

Year	1961	1972	1981	2005
Hospitals	07	07	07	07
Beds	208		310	
Dispensaries	21	39	50	--
Beds	29	48	57	
R.H.C	---	02	06	13
T.B Clinic	-----	02	02	02
BHU	--	--	--	71

But the latest information that there are one District Headquarters, 2 Tehsil Headquarter Hospitals, 4 M.C.H Centers, 3 Dispensaries, 13 Rural Health Centers and 71 basic health units (B.H.U) extending curative health services throughout the district. During the last three years 13 R. H. Cs has been upgraded to 20 hospitals. X-rays and dental care facilities have been provided in all the R. H. Cs More over three flying squads fully equipped with life

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saving drugs in order to provide health cover in case of road accident are available with headquarters at Khan Garh, Shahir Sultan & Alipur. All the B. H. Cs have been upgraded to 2 beds wards with the facilities of mother/child health care. About 850 lady health workers and 28 health supervisors are also working at the district level under P.M programme in addition to above-mentioned facilities. 28 In 1929 the progress of the health was as under;
 Health Centers

Year	Institutions	Out patient	Operation	Selected operation	Income	Expend- eture
1901	07	-	-	-	Local fund	14000
1926	16	249493	8736	656	2999	52221
1928	16	297073	10186	736	3193	59061
1929	19	321377	10904	823	3255	87275

Famous Hospital and dispensaries 1901 to 1980

District Headquarter Hospital Muzaffargarh
Civil Hospital Alipur
Civil Hospital Layyah
Civil Hospital Kotadu
Civil Hospital Sanawan
Civil Hospital Dera Din Panah
Police Hospital M.Garh
Canal Dispensary Punjad
Canal Dispensary y Taunsa Barrage
Canal Dispensary Tail Munda
Civil Dispensary Kot Sultan
Civil Dispensary Jotoi
Civil Dispensary Shahar Sultan
Civil Dispensary Rangpur
Civil Dispensary Khangarh
Civil Dispensary Karor
Civil Dispensary Seetpur
Rural Dispensary Basira
Rural Dispensary Kinghar
Rural Dispensary Rohillanwali
Rural Dispensary Langr Saris
Rural Dispensary Chaubara
Rural Dispensary Gujrat
Rural Dispensary Khairpur Sadat
Rural Dispensary Binda Ishaq
Rural Dispensary Muradpur Janoobi

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Rural Dispensary Kundrai

Mobile Dispensary

Educational point of view the district rank was 18th among the 28th district of province in the respect of literacy of its population. According to the census of 1901 the literacy ratio of the district was only 3.6 percent (6.5% male and 0.2% females). The number of pupils under instruction were 1612 in 1880 and 4106 in 1903-04. There were one special, three secondary and fifty eight primary public school with 14 advanced and eighty six elementary private schools. The public schools retuning 108 girls and the private schools 309. In the 1903-04 the expenditure on education was Rs.24000 the greater part of which was met by local funds.²⁹ The District is situated between two rivers; the Indus and the Chenab. A large number of population of this district belong to poor class which needs special attention the poor and needy people quit un-aware the importance of Education especially female education but their priorities are to earn the necessities of their life from early childhood. World food programme Authorities are providing great assistance to the poor and needy rural families in the shape of edible oil to promote primary Education for girls in the rural areas as well as to redress the issue of poverty alleviation in the most backward areas of Punjab such as Muzaffargarh.³⁰

If look at the traffic point of view there were only 49 vehicles registered in 1947. In 1948 the number of the registered vehicles were 165341 according to the report of excise and taxation department. Except the heavy traffic the district some small vehicles and carts are also found in the district. Motor buses and trucks are used in the Pacca roads for the transportation of the passengers and goods. Large numbers of Tangas are also seen in the towns. In the rural areas of the people used camels and donkeys for transportation and it is a very popular means of transportation in the rural areas.³¹

The British Govt. in India introduced the mail system first time after 1876. A postman was appointed for a village and he came in the village weekly. All the people hand over their letter to the postman and received their mail too. At that time they paid only three paise as a mail expenses. Post offices are also a very important source of communication in the district. There fore every main town of the district has its own post office with the passage of time. According to the 1981 census there were 244 post offices and a GPO is also located in the district. It is a very cheap an old way of communication. Except post offices there were 1647 telephone connections, 2 telegraph offices too. The every big town of the district has their own post offices now that were 79.³²

Post Offices

Sr.No.	Post offices
1	Muzaffargarh Head Office Muzaffargarh
2	Khangarh Post Office Khangarh
3	Shaher Sultan Post Office Shaher Sultan
4	Alipur Post Office Alipur
5	Dera Din Panah Post Office Dera Din Panah
6	Seetpur Post Office Seetpur
7	Layyah Post Office Layyah
8	Fatehpur Post Office Fatehpur

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9	Kot Sultan Post Office Kot Sultan
10	Karor Post Office Karor
11	Kotadu Post Office Kotadu
12	Kinjhar Post Office (Shahjmal)
13	Ghazi Ghat Post Office
14	Taunsa Barrage Post Office
15	Night Post Office GPO Muzaffargarh

District Gazetteer 1964, P. 254. & Census Reports 1961, 1972&1981

Year	Post Offices	Telegraph	Tele-phone
1921	-	01	-
1931	-	01	-
1941	-	01	-
1951	61	-	57
1961	79	02	122
1972	143	03	964
1981	244	20	1637

Conclusion

Khangerh was the headquarter of the district in 1849 but it was moved to Muzaffargarh in 1850. Tehsil Kotadu was part of Layyah district it was separated from Layyah in 1859 and added in Khangerh District. In 1859 the district Khangerh renamed as the district Muzaffargarh. In 1901 Layyah lost the status of Tehsil too. In 1909 Layyah again become a tehsil and it was added in the district of Muzaffargarh. After the emergence of Pakistan Muzaffargarh district was added in the Multan division. At the time of One Unite it was included in Bahawalpur State. After the ends of one unite it was again included in Multan division. It remained as the district of Multan division till 1st July 1982 at the creation of Dera Ghazi Khan Division. Now Muzaffargarh district is a district of Dera Ghazi Khan Division. Politically the people of the district were not very aggressive before the election 1945-46. The political sense has developed now and the golden example is the presidential election 1965 and the general election 1970 and 1977. while from the administrative point of view the district was under charge of Deputy Commissioner. He was District Magistrate and as well as a District collector. Local government system is also working to improve the condition of the people. Now it has decreased the authorities of Deputy Commissioner. The police department was established in 1861. The whole police staff was under the control of a superintendent police was also appointed to assist the deputy commissioner for administration. The whole district was divided into four police circles and 18 police stations. Judiciary is also a major pillar. There was a Session Judge and sub-judges were working for the justice in the district. With the passage of time their strength has increased.

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